

A Study on Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in Bharti Airtel at Tiruchirappalli Region

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ABSTRACT

This study helps to improve the SERVQUAL model as the foremost framework for investigating service quality. The relationships among customer satisfaction and service quality variables. The results exposed that all the service quality items were decent forecasters of customer satisfaction. For managers, this finding has significant implications with concern to brand building strategies. Indications of a successful brand building strategy are identify when companies afford quality services relation to other companies within the similar industry.

Keywords: Service quality, Customer satisfaction, SERVQUAL model, Customer service.

INTRODUCTION

The foremost global telecommunications is Bharti Airtel Limited company over 20 countries have operations in Asia and Africa which is Headquartered in New Delhi, India, the Company positions among the top three mobile service providers have worldwide subscribers. In India, the Company's aid exclude upto 4G wireless services, fixed line services, mobile commerce, DTH, enterprise services, high speed home broadband, with domestic and international long-distance services to carriers. In other geographies, it provides up to 4G wireless services and mobile commerce. Bharti Airtel had overall 372 Million worldwide customers at the finish of March 2017. The foremost provider is Airtel mobile telephony and it is the 2nd largest provider of fixed telephony in India, and is also provides with broadband with subscription of television services. Sunil Bharti Mittal headed Airtel brand and it

provides its telecom services globally. The first Indian telecom service is Bharti Airtel which offers to achieve Cisco Gold Certification. It also turns as a transporter for global distance communication services.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Aali, A. et al. (2011) identified the SERQUAL of mobile phone companies functioning in Saudi Arabia with the service quality instrument. It was created and developed with the alteration in customers' perceptions in nearly all the dimensions.

Chaudhary, A. et al. (2013) acknowledged the main dimensions of Telecom SERQUAL. The TOPSIS and AHP method with trapezoidal fuzzy numbers were used to recognize the dimensions of the service quality.

Bhargav, A. et al. (2014) investigated the gap between customers' expectations and perceptions in telecom sector. The primary data was collected with the help of a consistent questionnaire of service quality.

Sivanesan, R. (2013) studied the subscribers' attitude and perception on BSNL and AIRTEL services in Kanyakumari district. The researcher also identified the various problems faced by the customers in the district.

Khan, M. A. (2010) investigated the users' sensitivity of service quality of mobile telephone operators in Pakistan using a questionnaire survey covering SERVQUAL dimensions as well as network quality

and convenience as an additional dimensions. Convenience and network quality was found to be relatively most important dimensions.

Dabhade, N. et al. (2013) studied the impression of quality of service on customer satisfaction of mobile users by considering the case of Airtel and identified the factors that affect quality of services. This paper examined improvements in performance and it measures which were implemented up by the Airtel to improve customer satisfaction level.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the demographic profile of the customers of Bharti Airtel mobile service provider in Tiruchirappalli region.

- To identify customers preference towards the Bharti Airtel mobile service provider in Tiruchirappalli region.
- To measure the Service Quality of Bharti Airtel mobile Service provider in Tiruchirappalli region.

MEASUREMENT OF VARIABLES

Parasuraman, Zeithmal & Berry,1988; Ndubisi, Chan, & Chukwunonso, 2004 Service quality was restrained by expenditures the variables in SERVQUAL model. In using the SERVQUAL implement, 21 statements measured the service quality across these elements, using a seven point Likert scale. The influences in the model were measured as follows:

Tangibility: It refers to the presence of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, documents etc.

Reliability: It is the Ability to deliver the promised service perfectly and within a predefined time period.

Responsiveness: Responding to customer as and when required. In other word it requires

Good customer care service with willingness

Assurance: Knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence. This builds a tight and positive bonding between the customer and the service provider

Empathy: Empathy means understanding. The service provider must have a clear-cut understanding that what customer requires. Service providers must be Caring and should provide individual attention to customers.

Network Quality: It refers to the strength of the network and call quality.

SERVICE QUALITY GAP

In earlier service research, conference and more than chances of clients and consumers is a perception that has increased most attraction. This concept is all inclusive and cuts across service domains, but expectations change and experiences with alternate service providers could shape the customers' expectations. The important investigation gap here is attaining customers' expectation towards a particular service.

A gap is the difference, imbalance or disparity which is determined to exist between customers' perception of firm performance and their prior expectation. Service quality (SQ) perceived by customers is then as consequence of a contrast of customers' expectation (E) of facilities that the association should offer versus their perception of the performance (P) delivered by the service organization.

$$\text{Service Quality (SQ)} = \text{Customer's Expectations (E)} - \text{Customer's Perception (P)}$$

Expectations and perceptions of customers is management of service quality largely focuses on managing the gaps. The goal of the firm is to reduce the gap between (E) and (P). Rowley pointed out that previous scholars such as Lehtinen and Lehtinen and Gronroos also applied gap model similar to that upcoming by Parasuraman et al.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer Satisfaction has been a central concept in marketing fiction and is an important goal of all business activities. Today, companies face their toughest competition, because they move from a product and sales philosophy to a marketing philosophy, which gives a company a better chance of outperforming competition (Kotler, 2000). Overall customer satisfaction translates to more profits for companies and market share increase. The importance of customers has been highlighted by many researchers and academicians. The primary concern of promotion is to connect with customers by building a strong customer relationship in order to meet their expectations. Therefore, managers who see customers as the only way of profit, they consider. Customer satisfaction has a positive effect on an organization's profitability. The more customers are satisfied with products or services accessible, the more are chances for any successful business as customer satisfaction leads to repeat purchase, brand loyalty, and positive word of mouth marketing. Customer satisfaction leads to repeat purchases, loyalty and to customer retention (Zairi, 2000). Today most successful companies have taken the strategy of raising expectations and delivering performance to match. Such companies track their customers' expectations, perceived company presentation, and customer satisfaction. Highly satisfied customers produce several benefits for the company. Satisfied customers remain connected for a longer period and talk favorably to others about the company and its products and services.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION INFLUENCES OF PREPAID CUSTOMERS OF AIRTEL

Bharti Airtel mobile telecommunication industry, around are through and indirect factors that effect customer satisfaction. Here Research attention on the

Maximum significant factors that inspiration consumer satisfaction for prepaid consumers of Airtel which relates fundamentally with after sales services.

COST

The cost of the prepaid connection is one of major factor for the customers. Most of the people in India are low income level. Therefore, to attain more customers Airtel should not charge high price for the new connection so that it can be affordable to the low income people. Moreover, tariff of the prepaid packages must be judicious to keep satisfied its customers.

AVAILABILITY

Availability of the product at the right time leads the customers to a better experience. Customers always want the product to be availed near at home. They do not wish to go far to have product and other related services. Though, the prepaid customers require top-up their credit more frequently. So, to ensure frequent purchase and to build up long term relationship with the customers, the top-up stores should be conveniently located to the prepaid users.

CUSTOMER PERCEPTION

Customer perception is valuation approximately something watched and restrained and it contrasts from customers to customers, as individually customer takes changed opinions towards confident services and products that performance of significant role in determining customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is determined by the customers' perceptions and opportunities of the excellence of the products and services. In several cases, customer perception is independent, but it offers some useful understandings for organizations to improve their marketing strategies. Providing high level of quality service has become the selling point to attract customer's helpfulness and is the most significant driver that principals to satisfaction. Hence, customer perception and customer satisfaction are very thoroughly linked composed, because if the apparent service is near to customer's opportunities it principals to satisfaction. Satisfied customers deliver recommendations; maintain faithfulness towards the

company and customers in turn are additional likely to pay price dividends (Reichheld, 1996).

CONCLUSION

Airtel is a telecom service providing company where customer satisfaction is together goal and marketing tool. Today's customers in the telecom industry, where lots of offers are available, are harder to satisfy. They remain smoother, more challenging, more price conscious, less forgiving and they are innovative by many more companies with equivalent or better offers. The experiment is not only to produce satisfied customers also to produce loyal and delighted customer. This is competitive and customer driven market. It is high time for Airtel to satisfy and retain its existing customers. As the mobile connection price, call duty, even the price of the handset have been reduced due to technological advancement people of all income level are started using cell phone. Nowadays, most of the students and the low income people are deeply relying on Airtel because of the cheap cost. Hence, it has become inevitable for Airtel to expand the network coverage soon for a maintainable future.

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